

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS ON THE BEHAVIOUR OF CONCRETE MASONRY WALLS SUBJECTED TO FIRE

RAFAEL OLIVEIRA^{*}, JOÃO PAULO RODRIGUES^{*}, JOÃO PEREIRA[†] & PAULO LOURENÇO[†]

^{*} University of Coimbra, Department of Civil Engineering,
Rua Luís Reis Santos - Pólo II da Universidade, 3030-788 Coimbra, Portugal
E-mail: rafael.oliveira@uc.pt, jpaulocr@dec.uc.pt; webpage: <http://www.dec.uc.pt>

[†] University of Minho, Department of Civil Engineering
Campus de Azurém, 4800-058 Guimarães, Portugal
e-mail: jpereira@civil.uminho.pt, pbl@civil.uminho.pt; webpage: <http://www.civil.uminho.pt>

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ABSTRACT

Concrete masonry has been used worldwide all over centuries in loadbearing and partition walls. In Europe, the Standard EN 1996-1-2 (2005)¹ states that masonry walls must meet one or more requirements when exposed to fire. These requirements are I for temperature insulation, E for integrity to avoid the flow of smoke and hot gases through the wall, R for load-bearing capacity and M for mechanical impact.

In fire situations masonry walls are usually subjected to heating on one face, which leads to a thermal gradient through the thickness of the wall. In unrestrained walls, differential thermal expansion results in thermal bowing towards the fire, a complex phenomenon that depends on the wall's material's properties which are temperature dependent². The material properties degradation caused by high temperatures associated with the thermal displacements may lead to structural collapse of the wall³. In some cases, the structural stability (R) of masonry walls is required during the fire to prevent the global structural collapse, prevent fire spread, mitigate local structure collapse and guarantee the safe evacuation of building occupants⁴.

In the sequence of the previous research works, this paper presents a research on the structural behaviour of concrete masonry walls subjected to fire. Based on an experimental research previously performed on half-scale walls in fire situations, numerical models were developed and validated. Masonry walls were constituted by concrete blocks with calcareous aggregates and mortar M10. Numerical models were calibrated based on experimental studies performed by Haach (2009)⁵ and Lopes (2017)⁶ at ambient and high temperatures, respectively. The heat transfers and the mechanical analysis led to good agreement with the experimental values. The numerical models were validated and will be used in future researches to perform parametric studies.

The developed finite element models were validated against the experimental results. In this section, the numerical predictions of sample #1 are compared with the experimental results in thermal and structural domains.

To validate thermal response of the developed finite element model, a temperature history predicted by the model was compared with the experimental results. The temperature started to increase in an approximately constant rate up to the 90~100°C interval was reached. In this stage the free water in the constitutive materials started to evaporate and a plateau could be seen in the temperature-time curve.

The mechanical analysis was validated based on the vertical and horizontal displacements of the wall. The comparison of the numerical and experimental results are presented. The

vertical displacements started to grow from the beginning of the test due to the thermal elongation of the wall. During test #1, the effects of thermal expansion were more important than the reduction of the stiffness of the wall, positive displacements were found during the whole test. The numerical results were in good agreement with the experimental ones. The out-of-plane displacement started to grow from the beginning of the fire on the numerical model due to the thermal bowing of the wall.

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